

The Influence of Accounting Information Systems and Internal Control on the Quality of Regional Financial Statements in the Government of Bondowoso District

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ABSTRACT

This purpose of this research to determine the effect of accounting information systems and internal control systems on the quality of regional financial statements. In this study, the local government employees of Bondowoso Regency, the sample in this study were 50 respondents, financial and accounting staff at work units in Bondowoso. collected first using a questionnaire. The results of research conducted using SPSS prove that the independent variable accounting information system has a positive effect on local government financial reports and the internal control system has a positive effect on the quality of local government financial reports. So that local government financial reports will be able to meet the characteristics or value of information that improve the quality of local government financial reports, so that they get good opinions and have no exception a positive effect on the quality of regional financial reports. This study also has several limitations from several variables.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since 2004, regional autonomy has been implemented. However, in order to improve the welfare of the people in the regions, the main objective of regional autonomy has not yet been achieved. Even in Indonesia, along with the increasing demand for accountability of the central and local governments, various phenomena have emerged, which demonstrate this (Wilayah et al. n.d.) . Accountability can be described as a system of accountability for those in need (Septiana, Prasetyo, and Sulistiyo 2022).

The Governmental Accounting Standards Board (GASB 1999) in Concepts Statement No. 1 describes the purpose of financial statements on which the reporting of financial information will be used in government as a basis for decision making (Putra and Prabowo 2019). In accordance with PP standards to assess the quality of

financial reports (Pratama, Purnamawati, and Sayekti 2020). Regarding the Indonesian Government Accounting Standards No. 71 (PP RI 2010), understandable, relevant, reliable and comparable. *Book Collection 2001 Widjajanto, Nugroho "Accounting Information System / Nugroho Widjajanto; Yati Sumiharti" 2001* (Widjajanto 2001) argues that accounting information systems are "a variety of forms, records, settings for equipment, including computer and their equipment, communication tools, personnel, and coordinated reports. After careful design, financial data can be turned into information (H., Titisari, and . 2019) .

Internal control includes the policies and procedures used to achieve objectives, guarantee or provide reliable financial information, and ensure compliance with applicable laws and regulations (Pangesti Mulyono 2020) .

External factors or external environment are environmental conditions that are outside the control of the organization that have a significant effect on the plan *strategic* and operational plans, so that directly or indirectly affect the quality of output, in this case financial reports (Sukmaningrum and Harto 2012).

Basically, these external factors can be classified as the cause of the increase or decrease in the quality of financial statements (Azizah 2021). Organizations cannot avoid the influence of external factors outside the organization's own control, such as technological advances and regulatory changes (Kustono and Adi Nanggala 2020). Regional financial reporting must take advantage of this information technology (International and Of 2014). However, due to the absence of an adequate system, the level of utilization is usually not fully utilized, so it is necessary to check whether the area has implemented an accounting information system correctly (Mahendra, Winarno, and Kustono 2021).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Definition of Regional Financial Statements

Pradono and Basukianto (Pradono and Basukianto 2015) Explaining the Definition of Financial Statements Financial reports are records of information about an entity during an accounting period and can be used to describe the performance of the entity. The financial report is a structured report on the financial status and transactions conducted by the reporting entity (Putra et al. 2020).

Quality of Regional Financial Reports

In accordance with PP standards to assess the quality of financial reports (Miqdad and Izzalqurny 2019). Regarding the Indonesian Government Accounting Standards No. 71 of 2010, understandable, relevant, reliable and comparable (Komite Standar Akuntansi Pemerintahan 2016).

Accounting information system

Bodnar and Hopwood (Bodnar and Hopwood 2006) states that an information system is the process of converting or processing data into information. The stored data indicates that during this process, all input inputs will be processed as all outputs (Mahendra et al. 2021). The resulting incoming or outgoing data can be

stored, then reprocessed or new input is used when needed, or taken from storage to become useful information for information users (Nawang Sari, Junjuran, and Mulyono 2020).

Internal Control System

Government regulation number 60 (PP RI 2008) defines a control system Internal government (SPI) is a process of indispensable actions and activities Continuous leadership and all employees provide Have sufficient confidence in achieving goals Organize through effective activities Efficient and reliable financial reports, Safeguard state-owned assets and comply with Laws and regulations. SPI is a control activity, especially control of management information systems aimed at ensuring accuracy and completeness (Wardhaningrum and Kartika 2020).

HYPOTHESES

Effect of Accounting Information Systems

In line with the times, accounting information systems have become a convenient way to process data that is accurate, efficient, and safe, as well as a way to communicate between management in a fast and coordinated manner, so that financial data is transformed into necessary quality information. Given the importance of accounting information systems, the hypothesis is:

H1: The accounting information system has an influence on local government financial reports.

Influence of Internal Control Systems

As an activity carried out by leaders and employees, the internal control system is expected to provide assurance in terms of financial reporting activities, asset protection and compliance with applicable laws, ensuring accuracy, security, reliability, and effectiveness and efficiency. Based on this, the following hypothesis assumptions can be made:

H2: The internal control system affects the quality of local government financial reports

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Design and Type of Research

In this study, accounting information systems and the impact of internal control systems on the quality of local government financial reports used previous research and references from existing theories. The following hypotheses can be put forward, namely the

accounting information system, internal control system and its effect on the quality of local government financial reports as follows.

Population and Sample Taking Techniques

Population is the number of all objects (units / individuals) whose properties you want to estimate (Djarwanto 1985). The population of this research is the employees of the Regional Government of Bondowoso Regency, East Java . The sample is a number of individuals who represent the population. To provide more direction or pay more attention to the selection of samples that truly represent the population, a proportional stratified random sampling technique is used (Kustono, Mas, and Agustina 2020). Proportional stratified random sampling is a random sampling method and proportional stratified sampling from the population (Sugiyono 2010).

The sample in this study was the staff of the finance and accounting department at the Regional Work Unit (SKPD) of Bondowoso Regency . SKPDs studied were 30 SKPDs, using 50 resource persons who were finance and accounting staff at the Regional Work Units (SKPD) of Bondowoso Regency .

Data Analysis Metode

The analysis used in this research is quantitative analysis. Quantitative analysis aims to use statistical calculations to describe the relationship and influence between the dependent variable and the independent variable in the study (Moh., Purnamie, and Diah 2020). Description of Research Sample Sampling was carried out proportionally by calculating the percentage of the number of employees in each SKPD and calculated proportionally with the 50 samples used (Rachma, Somaji, and Kustono 2019) . Questionnaires were distributed among 50 and all questionnaires were returned with complete answers.

Descriptive statistics

The results of calculating the answers to the accounting information system indicator questionnaire show that the informants believe that the local government accounting information system is Bondowoso Regency (Society 2019) . East Java is very high. The indicator with the lowest score is the accounting system software that is in accordance with applicable laws and regulations (Wardhaningrum and Kartika 2020) .

At the same time, the highest indicator is to use the current accounting system that is compatible with SAP, and the Internet is already there and can be used properly (SUGIYONO, Miqdad, and Sulistiyo 2021) .

The results of calculating the answers to the questionnaire on the indicators of the internal control system showed that the informants believed that the local government internal control system in Bondowoso Regency, East Java was very high. The lowest indicator of an internal control system is that supervisors always determine responsible accounting policies and standards. Meanwhile, the highest indicator is the division of supervisory responsibilities. The questionnaire answers to this indicator indicate that the interviewee believed that the Bondowoso Regency Government in East Java was very high. The lowest indicator is that all employees understand the current government accounting rules and standards. At the same time, the highest indicator is that employees can interact and understand the system.

The results of calculating the answers to the questionnaire regarding external factor indicators indicated that the informants felt the external factors of the Bondowoso Regency local government. East Java is high. The lowest indicator is that the government has issued new regulations that change financial reporting as a whole, while the highest indicator is information technology which is currently changing rapidly (Prasetyo et al. 2020) .

The results of calculating the answers to the questionnaire can be used as an indicator of the quality of regional financial reports. This shows that most of the respondents considered it. The quality of regional financial reports in the Government of Bondowoso Regency, East Java is very high, this can be seen from the total score of 4.17 which shows that the informants really appreciate the quality of regional financial reports.

Classical Assumption Test and Multiple Regression

Multicollinearity test

Used to test whether there is a correlation between the independent variables and the regression model. The SPSS default value of the tolerance figure is greater than 0.10. This means that the tolerance for all variables to be included in the calculation of the regression model must be greater than 0.10. If it is less than 0.10, it can be

said that there is multicollinearity. At the same time, it is usually found that the variance inflation factor (VIF) is less than 10. This means that if the variable is greater than 10, there will be a multicollinearity problem with other independent variables (the correlation between the independent variables is very large) (Ghozali 2011). The following is the multicollinearity table as follows:

Table 1
Coefficient on Regression Output

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
The Accounting Information System	.825	1.213
The Internal Control System	.777	1.295
	.745	1.349

Coefficients 3

- a. Dependent Variable: Quality of regional financial reports

The influence of the accounting information system can be seen from the coefficient table above. In the internal control system, related to the quality of regional financial reports, the tolerance value is greater than the default value set at 0.10. At the same time, the VIF value is also displayed below the number 10, so it can be concluded that all variables meet the tolerance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.903	2.787		.673	.496		
The Accounting Information	.788	.113	.496	6.958	.000	.826	1.211
The internal control system	.216	.090	.166	2.301	.018	.775	1.291
SDM	.517	.123	.324	4.297	.000	.747	1.339

threshold requirements and the VIF value means accounting information system, internal control system. There is no multicollinearity problem in

the quality of regional financial reports, so that it can be resolved in the next test.

Heteroscedasticity test

Done so that the regression model has an inequality from the residuals of one observation to the residuals of other observations so that it can be applied to further tests. Based on the research results indicate that there is an influence between the accounting information system and the internal control system. There is no heteroscedasticity problem in the quality of regional financial reports. This can be proven by the high points that are scattered and randomly scattered above or below the number 0 on the Y axis. These points are irregular and do not form a certain pattern, so it can be concluded that the test has no problems.

The heteroscedasticity test is also carried out based on a statistical test, namely the Glejser test which is performed by regressing the absolute value of unstandardized residual error with independent variables. Based on the results of the Glejser test, it can be seen that all the significance values of the independent variables are greater than 0.05, so it can be said that heteroscedasticity does not occur in the model.

Normality test

Designed to test the regression model, the dependent variable and the independent variable are both normally distributed (Ghozali 2011). High regression models have a normal distribution or approach a normal distribution. The first way is to pass the graph test, according to the picture, it can be seen that the data is moving in the direction and approaching of the diagonal, so it can be said that the data is normally distributed. To find out in detail whether the data is normally distributed, you can use the Kolmogorov-Smimov test by testing the residual results. From regression analysis. This can be seen from the test results of Asymp Sig (0.231) > 0.05 so that there are no significant variables. Thus it can be said that the data is normally distributed. Multiple linear regression between accounting information systems. Regarding the internal control system on the quality of regional financial reports, the following results can be obtained:

Table 2
Multiple Linear Regression Equation Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis testing is used to test assumptions about the regression coefficient, namely to find out whether the regression equation obtained is reasonable.

Hypothesis Test t Test

Table 3

Result of t count

Variabel	t	Sig.
Accounting Information System	6.958	.000
Internal Control System	2.402	.018

Get meaningful results based on the results calculated Equals $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that the accounting information system has a positive effect on the quality of regional financial reports. This interpretation means that if the accounting information system is improved, the quality of regional financial reports will also improve. The significance of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that H_1 is accepted.

Based on the results of the calculation, the results obtained a significance of $0.018 < 0.05$. This shows that the internal control system has a positive impact on quality of regional financial reports. The significance of $0.018 < 0.05$ indicates that H_2 is accepted. This interpretation may imply that if the internal control system is improved, the quality of regional financial reports will also improve.

F test (Goodness of Fit)

Combined hypothesis test is a test to determine the effect of the Accounting Information System. The internal control system affects the quality of regional financial reports. Based on the calculation results, the calculated F value obtained from the complete calculation is 47,740, and the result is Significance 0,000, and degrees of freedom are in numbers 3 and 99 in the table, table value is 2.70, then F counts $47.740 > F$ table value = 2.70 (valid), valid value $0.000 < 0.05$ means that H_0 is rejected h_a has been accepted. This describes the accounting information system. The internal control system also has a significant influence on the quality of regional financial reports, or it can be said that this model is the right way to predict the quality of regional financial reports.

Model testing (suitability)

Combined hypothesis test is a test to determine the influence of the quality of the accounting information system, internal control system, regional financial reports. Based on the results of the calculation, it shows that the calculated F value obtained from the complete calculation results is 21.521, namely the results of the Significance of 0.000, and the degrees of freedom respectively in tables 7 and 99, and F table 2.10, so that F is calculated $21.521 > F$ table = 2.10 (valid), and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating that H_0 is rejected, H_a can be accepted. This indicates that the accounting information system and internal control system which are influenced by external factors have a significant influence on the quality of regional financial reports, or it can be said that this model is the right method to predict the quality of regional financial reports.

4. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

Conclusion and Implication

The accounting information system has a positive impact on the quality of regional financial reports. By optimizing the use of sophisticated information technology to build management information systems and workflow networks, so as to facilitate access between work units and improve the quality of financial report information, so that the government can work in an integrated manner. The internal control system has a positive impact on the quality of regional financial reports. With a good internal control system, local government financial reports will be able to meet the characteristics/value of information that improve the quality of financial report.

Suggestion

the local government, so that it gets a good opinion, is not without a positive effect on the quality of regional financial reports. This happens because changes usually cannot be done quickly, but these changes must be made through the bureaucracy first, so changes in external factors usually take a long time to result in changes in the quality of financial statements.

Limitations

In this study, based on the results of the coefficient of determination (R^2), the study has several limitations. The results showed that the

Adjusted R Square value was 58.6%, although the coefficient of determination can be seen from the coefficient of determination after the adjustment variable affects the strength of the relationship. This value increased from 58.6% to 59.2%, which means that there are other factors that contributed 40.8%, this can be explained by other variables that affect the quality of local government financial reports, such as government accounting standards.

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